

THORIUM. ITS SEPARATION AND ESTIMATION. THE IODATE METHOD

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It is shown that thorium can be estimated by precipitation with iodic acid in nearly neutral solutions and may also be freed from uranium. In 4*N*-nitric acid solution iodic acid frees thorium from cerite earths in two precipitations. This method is an improvement on the classical method in that the precipitate can be weighed directly. Thorium in monazite has been successfully determined in this way.

The best known method for the separation of thorium from the cerite earths is that of Meyer and Speter (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1910, 34, 306) but it suffers from the serious disadvantage that the composition of the precipitate is uncertain and consequently a direct determination by weighing the precipitate is not possible. Recently, however, Moeller and Fritz (*Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 42, 63) have shown that the precipitate is the normal iodate but difficulties arise in washing the same free of adsorbed iodate and nitric acid, chief of which are the solubility of the precipitate and its hydrolysis in the comparatively large quantities of water necessary to remove the sparingly soluble potassium iodate. As a result, the thorium recovery in their experiments is about 99%. Prior to the appearance of this publication, we carried out a number of experiments employing iodic acid, for preliminary studies with potassium iodate indicated that in neutral solution the precipitate approximated to a basic iodate of the composition $\text{ThO}_2 \cdot 2\text{Th}(\text{IO}_3)_4$, while in the presence of acid the normal tetraiodate resulted always. Our procedure with iodic acid is not subject to the failings mentioned by Moeller and Fritz. (*loc. cit.*). The removal of iodic acid is easy on account of its high solubility; and normal iodate precipitates under all conditions. We have also determined in a semi-quantitative manner the thorium loss through solubility and hydrolysis. Our conclusions are that the solubility of normal thorium iodate in water at the room temperature (about 26°) is negligibly small, as will be evident from the following simple experiment.

Moist thorium iodate (5 g.) was shaken up with 200 c.c. of water for 5 hours and filtered. The filtrate (100 c.c.) on concentration to 10 c.c. failed to give a colorimetric test capable of detecting 0.01 mg of thorium per c.c. Thus, the quantity, if any, of thorium passing into solution is less than 0.04 mg. per 100 c.c. Error resulting from the effect of hydrolysis appears, however, to be of a higher magnitude. In a similar experiment titration with thiosulphate of the iodate ion in solution indicated a concentration of 0.8 mg. in 100 c.c. If on the other hand a mixture of equal volumes of alcohol and water is used, the hydrolysis is considerably suppressed and amounts to only a third of that in water alone. This of course does not represent the magnitude of the error in an actual determination; it is indeed much smaller. In the iodic acid procedure described below, it will be seen that there is a great simplification of the process with a substantial increase in accuracy.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

When Thorium is present alone or is admixed with Uranium.—The thorium solution, if acid, is rendered neutral or but faintly acid to congo red by careful addition of dilute ammonia (potassium or sodium hydroxide is not recommended on account of the lower solubility of these iodates) and heated to 60° to 70°. A 2.5% aqueous solution of iodic acid is added in slight excess and the resulting heavy precipitate is left to settle in a warm place. This takes about 15 to 30 minutes. The supernatant liquid is poured through a Jena glass crucible No 4, the precipitate is washed by decantation in the beaker 4 or 5 times with 0.25% iodic acid, transferred to the crucible and finally washed with 20 to 25 c.c. of cold water. On drying at 105° for 3 to 4 hours the precipitate corresponds to the composition, $\text{Th}(\text{IO}_3)_4$ and may be weighed as such. Some results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Thorium taken.	Wt. of thorium iodate obtained.	Wt. of thorium calc.	Error.
0.2110 g.	0.8484 g.	0.2113 g.	+0.0003 g.
0.2110	0.8481	0.2112	+0.0002
0.2015	0.8090	0.2015	—
—	0.8083	0.2013	—0.0002
—	0.8104	0.2018	+0.0003
—φ	0.8090	0.2015	—
—φ	0.8098	0.2017	+0.0002

φ In these estimations a quantity of uranyl nitrate corresponding to 0.20 g. of UO_3 was present.

When Thorium is admixed with Cerite Earths.—In neutral or faintly acid solution both thorium and the cerite earths are precipitated, while if the solution is too acid (6N and above) the thorium is incompletely precipitated. An extended investigation has shown that the acidity of the solution should remain at a minimum p_H ; the iodate ion concentration also should at least approximately be regulated. A 3.5% solution of iodic acid in 5N-nitric acid yields the best results. About 150 c.c. of the reagent are necessary to precipitate completely 0.1 to 0.2 g. of thorium. The procedure is as follows:

To the thorium solution (10 to 25 c.c.) are added in a thin stream with constant stirring about 150 c.c. of the cold reagent and the precipitate is allowed to settle for half an hour. It is then filtered through a Jena glass crucible (No.4), washed first with 0.35% iodic acid in 0.5N-nitric acid and then with 25 to 40 c.c. of cold water. Washing with cold water is withheld when a double precipitation is resorted to. In this case the precipitate is dissolved in 25 c.c. of concentrated nitric acid and suitably diluted so as to give a solution 4 to 5 normal in nitric acid. A saturated solution of 5 g. of iodic acid in water is then added. It is important that the overall concentration of nitric acid should not fall below 4N, and the iodic acid concentration should be at least 3%. The following table shows the results obtained.

TABLE II

Wt. of ThO ₂ taken.	Wt. of cerite earths (oxide) added.	Wt. Th(IO ₃) ₄ obtained.	Wt. of ThO ₂ calc.	Error.
0.1140g.	—	0.4038g. φ	0.1145g.	+0.0005g.
"	—	0.4035 φ	0.1144	+0.0004
"	0.0280 g.	0.4032 φ	0.1142	+0.0002
"	"	0.4030	0.1142	+0.0002
"	0.1402	0.4160 φ	0.1179	+0.0039
"	"	0.4031	0.1141	+0.0001
"	1.1424	0.4032	0.1142	+0.0002
"	"	0.4027	0.1140	—
* Monazite				
0.0900 g.	0.4708	0.3182	0.0902	+0.0002
"	"	0.3185	0.0903	+0.0003

φ These figures refer to values obtained on single precipitation.

* Monazite concentrate containing ThO₂, 0.0900 g. + $\frac{1}{2}$ Ce₂O₃, 0.4708 g.

C O N C L U S I O N

Thorium can be conveniently precipitated and estimated as Th(IO₃)₄ in nearly neutral solution by using iodic acid as precipitant. This provides also a method for separating *thorium* from *uranium*.

In the presence of nitric acid, about 4N, iodic acid separates thorium completely from the cerite earths in two precipitations; the final precipitate may be weighed directly. When the quantity of cerite earths is small, less than a tenth of the thorium concentration, complete separation takes place in a single precipitation. Thorium in monazite can be accurately estimated by this method in much shorter time than in the classical iodate method.